

Tourism Corporate Social Responsibility Effects on Purchase Intention during Covid-19: Mediating Role of Trust and Moderating Role of Trust Propensity

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ABSTRACT: Though the pyramid model of corporate social responsibility, the paper classified tourism corporate social responsibility into economic responsibility, legal responsibility, ethical responsibility, charitable responsibility and environmental responsibility. With the COVID-19 epidemic as the background, based on 250 questionnaire data, the paper proposed a structural equation model that explore the impact mechanism of tourism corporate social responsibility on tourist purchase intention during the COVID-19 epidemic. The mediation effect of trust was examined in the model. And the question whether trust propensity plays a moderating role was answered.

The results of experimental studies revealed that: First, the economic responsibility, ethical responsibility and charitable responsibility have a significant positive effect on tourist purchase intention during the epidemic period. Second, trust plays a partial mediating role in the relationship between tourism corporate social responsibility and tourist purchase intention. Third, trust propensity has no moderating effect on the relationship between tourism corporate social responsibility and tourist purchase intention. Suggestions for tourism enterprises was put forwarded: except ensuring the quality of tourism products, enterprises should take corporate social responsibility into consideration of the long-term management decisions. Especially in the event of major events (COVID-19), it is more important to show the responsibility of enterprises.

KEYWORDS: COVID-19 epidemic, tourism corporate social responsibility, purchase intention, trust, trust propensity, structural equation model

I. INTRODUCTION

During the Chinese New Year in 2020, the novel coronavirus epidemic heavily hit. Due to its high infectivity and mortality rate, it has caused great panic around the world, and has dealt a heavy blow to various industries, especially to tourism. Now, the epidemic situation in China is weak, but the epidemic continues to spread in some other regions. The "confrontation" between human beings and the epidemic continues. Since the outbreak of the epidemic, the world has worked together to fight it, including many tourism companies. On the one hand, some tourism enterprises adhered to the bottom line of ethics. They gave priority to the health and safety of tourists and employees, prevented the flow of people and prevented the spread of epidemic diseases caused by tourism. After the situation eased, they set up anti-epidemic equipment in accordance with the law, actively resumed work and production, and worked hard to create wealth and profits. On the other hand, tourism companies did their best to control the epidemic, for example, 24 million yuan was donated in the first time after the outbreak of the epidemic, and hotels and scenic spots were used as isolation sites. However, tourism enterprises themselves were faced with huge survival pressure when suffered from such a horrible disaster. They would inevitably have a large amount of cash outflow, resulting in the loss of human and material resources when they undertake social responsibilities. Then why are some tourism companies willing to undertake corporate social responsibility? Are there economic benefits or other benefits for tourism enterprises to undertake social responsibility?

In the past decade, a large number of literatures with the theme of "corporate social responsibility" have been published. As a that has been concerned by the academic circle, many mature theoretical achievements have been accumulated. In recent years, the enterprise category of corporate social responsibility has gradually diversified, and the tourism corporate social

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responsibility has begun to attract attention. Under the influence of the COVID-19 outbreak, "corporate social responsibility under COVID-19" has become one of the research hotspots.

The purchase behaviour of consumers is the main source of enterprise income, while Morrison (1979) proved that the purchase intention of consumers to an enterprise determines their purchase behaviour to a large extent. The more positive the intention, the more likely it is to produce a purchase. With the hot social issues this year and the study trend in this field, it is of great theoretical and practical significance to investigate whether tourism enterprises can positively influence the purchasing intention of tourists by assuming social responsibilities. This paper uses the questionnaire survey method to explore the impact mechanism. Moreover, this paper innovatively adds "trust" and "trust propensity" as intermediate variables, to explore whether "trust" plays a mediating role between tourism corporate social responsibility and tourist purchasing intentions, and to explore whether "trust propensity" plays a moderating role between independent variables and dependent variables, so as to provide certain reference for academic researchers in this field. To sum up, this paper will investigate "the impact of tourism enterprises' social responsibility on tourist purchase intention during COVID-19, and explore the mediating role of trust and the moderating role of trust propensity".

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Tourism Corporate Social Responsibility

Scholars from various countries have their own opinions on the definition of corporate social responsibility, no unified opinions. In 1924, Oliven. Mr Shelton first coined "corporate social responsibility (CSR)" in his book "The Philosophy of Management". After that, scholars gave different definitions of corporate social responsibility: In 1953, Bowen, a pioneer in this field, defined it as an enterprise behavior that makes decisions and implements with feasible value for the purpose of realizing social pursuit. Carroll (1979) showed that corporate social responsibility is the economic and social expectations placed by the public on an organization in a specific period. With great significance, he was the first one who divided corporate social responsibility into four parts: Economic responsibility, legal responsibility, ethical responsibility and charitable responsibility, and the constructor of the famous corporate social responsibility pyramid model (1991). He created a precedent for the study of corporate social responsibility who provided a theoretical basis for future research. Corporate social responsibility as defined by Carroll is comprehensive and widely cited, so did the pyramid model.

At first, some companies sacrificed social responsibility to achieve their economic goals. But In recent years, entrepreneurs have gradually realized the benefits of taking corporate social responsibility and begun to take the initiative to take social responsibility. At the same time, scholars have also done more research to improve the theory of corporate social responsibility. Social corporate responsibility was divided into basic responsibility and social responsibility (Bai Quanli and Wang Yawen, 2000). From the perspective of stakeholders, Zhou Zucheng (2005) believed that corporate social responsibility includes economic responsibility, legal responsibility and moral responsibility. When environmental problems became more and more concerned, Ma Hongzhuan (2012) added environmental responsibility as a new corporate social responsibility on the basis of the four dimensions of "pyramid model". At first, scholars' study on corporate social responsibility focused on the concept and ethical responsibility. Gradually, the study on the basic theory of corporate social responsibility, research on the relationship between corporate social responsibility and consumers and relationship with enterprise performance have become the focus of the study field.

However, there are few studies on the sub-section, tourism corporate social responsibility, in academic areas, among which, Su Lujun (2012) found through a questionnaire survey that the social responsibility of tourist destinations positively influences tourist loyalty." It is only in recent years that tourism corporate social responsibility has been paid attention to, so there is a lot of research space. Based on the "pyramid model" and stakeholder theory, we define tourism corporate social responsibility as the economic, legal, ethical, charitable and environmental responsibilities that tourism enterprises bear for their stakeholders, such as tourists, employees, communities and shareholders, in the process of operation.

B. Purchase Intention

Purchase Intention, or PI for short, is an important category of consumer behavior theory. Dodds (1991) defined consumer purchase intention earlier. He believed that consumer purchase intention was the possibility of consumers to purchase a specific product or service. By summarizing the definition of purchase intention by many scholars, it is concluded that purchase intention is a kind of psychological expression of consumers subjectively. Since the 1990s, scholars at home and abroad have paid much attention to the research on the influence of consumers' purchase intention. Among them, there were studies on the impact of corporate social responsibility on consumers' purchase intention, and the influence mechanism was divided into direct influence

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and indirect influence. In terms of direct impact, scholars mainly explored the impact of corporate social responsibility on consumers' purchasing intention by combining the perception of CSR (Ki-Hoon Lee and Dongyoung Shin, 2009) and the types of corporate social responsibility (Zhou Zucheng and Zhang Yijie, 2007). In terms of indirect influence, many scholars have explored the intermediate role of corporate reputation (Xie Peihong and Zhou Zucheng, 2009), consumer characteristics (Lisa and Patrick, 2016) and so on. No matter what kind of influence, most of the conclusions studied by scholars are that CSR has a positive effect on purchase intention (Gao Duanxun and Fang Wenchang, 2012; Han Enqing and Liu Enya, 2003, etc.). Combined with the academic definition of purchase intention, this paper holds that purchase intention is consumers' purchasing attitude towards a product or service due to internal reasons or external influences.

However, there is a lack of study on "the impact of tourism corporate social responsibility on tourist purchasing intentions" by scholars, and few references can be found through website retrieval. At present, the existing study on tourism corporate social responsibility mainly focuses on the relationship between corporate social responsibility and financial performance. And the types of enterprises studied are mostly travel agencies. There are few studies on the relationship between tourism corporate social responsibility and tourist, among which, Ma Hongzhan (2013) concluded through questionnaire survey that "corporate social responsibility of travel agencies has a positive impact on public buying intentions".

C. Trust

The influence mechanism of trust on social and market exchange relations is a common study topic in many academic fields. Trust can occur between individuals, between individuals and organizations, and between organizations. Different study fields and perspectives make the academic circles have different definitions of trust. In the field of marketing, trust is regarded as a core construct of relationship marketing theory. Trust was defined as "confidence in the reliability and sincerity of the other party with whom one has an exchange relationship" (Morgan and Hunt, 1994). With the deepening of scholars' study on trust, trust is gradually divided into multi-dimensional dimensions. This paper also plans to divide trust into multi-dimensional dimensions to conduct research. It was believed that competence, kindness and integrity determine the level of trust among people in an organization (Mayer et al., 1995). Later, trust was divided into computing trust, knowledge trust and consistency trust (Lewicki and Bunker, 1996). Based on the classification of trust by the above scholars and the particularity of the COVID-19, this paper divides trust into trust based on ability, trust based on integrity and trust based on consistency.

D. Trust propensity

Trusting propensity is often used to explore the influence of personality traits. Rotter (1971) is the first one who put forward the concept of trust propensity, believing that trust propensity is "an expectation of a person or a group on the trustworthiness of others or things". There are differences in trust propensity between both individuals and groups. In the field of behavioral science, some scholars have studied the moderating or mediating effect of trust propensity on attitude and behavior. The moderating effect of trust propensity was researched, finding that trust propensity played a moderating role between social responsibility and brand equity of tourism destination (Wang Chunyang et al, 2020). Zhou Tiantian (2021) concluded that trust propensity plays an intermediary role between the individual characteristics of consumers and their consumption intention. This paper is going to explore whether trust propensity has a moderating effect on the relationship between tourism corporate social responsibility and tourist purchase intention.

III. RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS AND MODEL CONSTRUCTION

A. Impact of tourism corporate social responsibility

Matthew (2017) found that before making purchases, corporate social responsibility behavior has influence on consumers' decisions. In today's fierce market competition, many enterprises have not only regarded products as their only competitiveness, but also regarded corporate social responsibility as a strategic tool, and established a good relationship with stakeholders, so as to promote the long-term development of enterprises. This is an era of information explosion, the influence of information surrounding products on consumers is also getting bigger when the speed of acquiring and perceiving information is getting faster. Consumers' perception of corporate social responsibility will undoubtedly positively influence their attitude towards enterprises, thus generate their purchase intention. In order to further studies "tourism corporate social responsibility impact on purchase intention", especially to explore whether the influence relationship still holds in such a special period, this paper will further discuss the impact of different dimensions of tourism corporate social responsibility on purchase intention. Thus, making assumptions and drawing hypothetical model 1 as shown in the figure below:

H1: Economic responsibility of tourism enterprises has a positive impact on tourist purchase intention

H2: Legal responsibility of tourism enterprises has a positive impact on tourist purchase intention

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H3: Ethical responsibility of tourism enterprises has a positive impact on tourist purchase intention

H4: Charity responsibility of tourism enterprises has a positive impact on tourist purchase intention

H5: Environmental responsibility of tourism enterprises has a positive impact on tourist purchasing intention

Figure 1. Assumption Model 1

B. Trust as a mediator

Trust has always been a topic of academic concern, and there have been many mature theoretical results. Although scholars have different study fields and perspectives on the effect of trust on consumers' purchase intention, most study results show that trust has a positive effect on purchase intention. And Luo Longfei (2012), through empirical research, concluded that "brand trust is an intermediate variable between corporate social responsibility and consumers' purchase intention". Accordingly, this paper proposes the following hypotheses:

H6: Consumer trust plays a partial mediating role between social responsibility and purchase intention

C. Trust propensity as a moderator

Consumers face great uncertainty risks when purchasing products (Kaplan et al, 1974). Richardson (1994) believed that when consumers lack product or service information, they will perceive product value through external information, and external cues have higher confidence value for consumers. And trust propensity is a variable that is highly correlated with trust. Chen Yue (2015) believed that individuals or groups with high trust propensity tend to have trust, and their risk perception level will be reduced, thus, affecting their attitude and behavior. Therefore, the following hypotheses are proposed:

H7: trust propensity plays a moderating role in the relationship between tourism corporate social responsibility and tourist purchase intention.

Research model is shown in Figure2.

Figure 2. Assumption Model 2

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IV. RESULT

A. Questionnaire Design and Distribution

The questionnaire includes six parts: demographic information of the tourists, frequency of travel, perception of tourism corporate social responsibility, purchase intention, trust and trust propensity. Scientific and rigorous maturity scale was referred to design the questionnaire. Combined with the background of COVID-19, the questionnaire factor measurement indexes were formulated. The measurement items were evaluated using 5-point Likert scale, with 1-5 indicating "disagree", "disagree", "generality", "relatively agree" and "strongly agree". The demographic characteristics of the respondents included gender, age, education background, occupation and income range. In terms of the number of trips, the frequency of travel was collected, so was the number of trips to the travel destinations of OCT Group in one year. The following table shows the references to the measurement indicators of questionnaire factors:

Table 1. References to Questionnaire Indicators

Factors	References	Item matrix dimension
Economic responsibility	Carroll(1991)、 LEE SANGHEUN(2020) et al	5
Legal responsibility	Carroll(1991)、 LEE SANGHEUN(2020) et al	5
Charitable responsibility	Carroll(1991)、 LEE SANGHEUN(2020) et al	5
Ethical responsibility	Carroll(1991)、 LEE SANGHEUN(2020) et al	3
Environmental responsibility	Carroll(1991)、 LEE SANGHEUN(2020) et al	3
Purchase intention	Bagozzi (2001), LEE SANGHEUN (2020), Zhou Wenhui (2008), et al	4
Trust propensity	Lee (2001), Li Haiqin (2010)	4
Capacity trust	McAllister (1995)	4
Integrity and trust	Sirdeshmukh (2002)	4
Consistency trust	Lewicki、 Stevenson(1999)	4

The questionnaire was issued officially after having been revised. Considering that the subjects of the study were tourists, the questionnaire was distributed in two ways: offline and online. On March 21, 2021 and March 22, 2021, we went to the scenic spots of OCT Group to distribute questionnaires so as to directly obtain the cognition and views of tourists. Limited by experience and resources, the offline survey was only conducted in Shenzhen Happy Valley and Window of the World. On the other hand, the author made a rigorous electronic questionnaire on the questionnaire production platform and published it online for the subjects to fill in. The survey time for the offline part was from March 21, 2021 to March 25, 2021. In order to improve the recovery rate and the truthfulness of the answers, the questionnaire was anonymous.

A total of 363 questionnaires were sent out and 363 were recovered with a recovery rate of 100%. The number of effective questionnaires was 250 and the effective rate was 69%. There were 17 questionnaire survey items, and the sample size was 15 times that of the item (Baumgartner et al,1978), which ensured the authority of the results.

B. Data analysis

According to the results in Table 2, it can be seen from the data analysis results of "gender" that the proportion of women in this questionnaire sample was higher than that of men, exceeding 31.2%. According to the analysis results of "age", the group with the largest proportion was "16-25 years old", the sample of "26-25 years old" accounted for 14.8%, and the respondents of these two age groups accounted for 81.2%. In terms of "educational background", "undergraduate/junior college" accounted for 73.6%, the largest proportion. Relatively, the "occupation" of the respondents was evenly distributed, but the proportion of "full-time students" was relatively high, accounting for 34.4%. In the sample, the distribution of "income" was also relatively uniform, with "20,000 yuan or above" accounting for the least (7.6%). As shown in Table 3, the data analysis results of the number of tourists showed that the number of tourists who travel "2-5 times" each year is the largest, while the number of tourists who travel to the scenic spots of OCT Group is more like "1", accounting for 35.6%.

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Table 2. Demographic Frequency Analysis of the Samples

Variable	Options	Frequency	Percentage	Average value	Standard deviation
Gender	Male	86	34.4%	1.66	0.48
	Female	164	65.6%		
Age	15 and below	13	5.2%	2.44	0.97
	16-25	166	66.4%		
	26-35	37	14.8%		
	36-45	16	6.4%		
	46-60	17	6.8%		
	61 and above	1	0.4%		
Education	Junior high school and below	12	4.8%	2.82	0.62
	Secondary	37	14.8%		
	Undergraduate/Specialist	184	73.6%		
	Postgraduate/Doctor	17	6.8%		
occupation	Full - time students	86	34.4%	6.19	5.27
	Operating personnel	10	4.0%		
	Salesman	23	9.2%		
	Market / PR Staff	10	4.0%		
	Customer service staff	9	3.6%		
	Administrative/Logistics staff	6	2.4%		
	Human resources	6	2.4%		
	Finance/Audit staff	9	3.6%		
	Civilian/Clerical staff	10	4.0%		
	Technical personnel	17	6.8%		
	/R & D personnel				
	administrative staff	3	1.2%		
	teacher	19	7.6%		
	Consultant	4	1.6%		
	Professionals (e.g. accountants, lawyers, architects, paramedics, journalists)	5	2.0%		
	other	33	13.2%		
	Income(RMB)	0	44		
2000 below		34	13.6%		
2000-5000		54	21.6%		
5000-10000		73	29.2%		
10000-20000		26	10.4%		
	20000 and above	19	7.6%		

Table 3. Number of Trips of Respondents

Variable	Options	Frequency	Percentage	Average value	Standard deviation
Number of trips	1	79	31.6%	1.87	0.79
	2-5 sessions	141	56.4%		
	6-8	13	5.2%		
	8 or more	17	6.8%		
Overseas Chinese Town	1	134	53.6%	1.63	0.82

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Brand Scenic Spot	2-5 sessions	89	35.6%
	6-8	13	5.2%
	8 or more	14	5.6%

Tables below display the results of reliability and validity analysis using SPSS software. The Cronbach's α of the "Social Responsibility of Tourism Enterprises", "purchase intention", "trust" and "trust propensity" are 0.968, 0.909, 0.977, 0.930 respectively, all are greater than 0.8 (Table 4). Therefore, the reliability of the scale is good. Validity refers to the accuracy of the sample data. The higher the validity, the more consistent the data are with the real characteristics of the measured indicators. In this paper, the validity of the data was tested. According to Table 5, Table 6, Table 7 and Table 8, the KMO of the "social responsibility of tourism enterprises", "purchase intention", "trust" and "trust propensity" are 0.953, 0.798, 0.963, 0.833 respectively, all are great than 0.7. And all the significance of Bartlett's sphericity test were infinitely close to $0 < 0.05$. Therefore, the validity of the scale is good, which means they meet the criteria of "suitable for factor analysis".

Table 4. Reliability Analysis of Tourism Corporate Social Responsibility Scale

Factors	Cronbach's α
Tourism corporate social responsibility	0.968
Economic responsibility	0.853
Legal responsibility	0.915
Ethical Responsibility	0.955
Charitable Responsibility	0.929
Environmental responsibility	0.900
Purchase intention	0.909
Trust	0.977
Ability trust	0.942
Integrity trust	0.951
Consistency trust	0.948
Trust propensity	0.930

Table 5. Validity Analysis of Tourism Corporate Social Responsibility

KMO and Bartlett tests		
KMO sampling fitness quantity		.953
Bartlett's test for sphericity	Approximate chi-square	5169.075
	Degree of freedom	210
	significant	.000

Table 6. Purchasing Intention Validity Analysis

KMO and Bartlett tests		
KMO sampling fitness quantity		.798
Bartlett's test for sphericity	Approximate chi-square	780.215
	Degree of freedom	10
	significant	.000

Table 7. Trust Validity Analysis

KMO and Bartlett tests		
KMO sampling fitness quantity		.963
Bartlett's test for sphericity	Approximate chi-square	3847.189
	Degree of freedom	78
	significant	.000

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Table 8. Trust Propensity Validity Analysis

KMO and Bartlett tests		
KMO sampling fitness quantity		.833
Bartlett's test for sphericity	Approximate chi-square	818.314
	Degree of freedom	10
	significant	.000

In this questionnaire design, all factors and items were referred to the maturity scale. Therefore, exploratory factor analysis will not be carried out on the questionnaire, but confirmatory factor analysis will be. In terms of structural validity analysis, the software used in this paper is AMOS, and the analysis results are as table below (table 9). According to the fitting indexes ($X^2 / DF = 2.583$, $RMSEA = 0.08$, $CFI = 0.946$, $TLI = 0.935$, and $NFI = 0.915$), the structural validity of the comprehensive measurement model is good. The fitting indexes of the "tourism corporate social responsibility" scale, $X^2 / DF = 2.583$, $RMSEA = 0.08$, $CFI = 0.946$, $TLI = 0.935$, $NFI = 0.915$, indicate good structural validity of the tourism corporate social responsibility scale. The fitting indexes of the "trust" scale were $X^2 / DF = 2.583$, $RMSEA = 0.08$, $CFI = 0.946$, $TLI = 0.935$, $NFI = 0.915$, indicating that the structure validity of the trust scale was good. Therefore, further structural model analysis can be carried out.

Table 9. Structural Validity

	x^2/df	RMSEA	CFI	TLI	NFI
Integrated measurement model	2.561	0.079	0.911	0.903	0.862
Corporate social responsibility in tourism	2.583	0.08	0.946	0.935	0.915
Trust	2.084	0.066	0.938	0.981	0.974

SPSS software was used for correlation analysis (Table 10). At the significance level of 0.01, the correlation coefficient between each dimension of tourism corporate social responsibility and purchase intention is > 0.5 , which indicates that at the significance level of 0.01, economic responsibility, legal responsibility, ethical responsibility, charitable responsibility, environmental responsibility and purchase intention are all positively correlated. The higher the perception of tourism corporate social responsibility, the greater the degree of purchase intention. The correlation coefficient of each dimension of tourism corporate social responsibility and capacity-based trust, integrity-based trust, consistent-based trust is > 0.5 , indicating that at 0.01 significant level, economic responsibility, legal liability, ethics responsibility, charitable responsibility, environmental responsibility and trust have positive correlation. The correlation coefficient between each dimension of trust and purchase intention is > 0.7 at the significance level of 0.01, which indicates that at the significance level of 0.01, ability trust, integrity trust, consistency trust and purchase intention have a positive correlation.

Table 10. Correlation Analysis

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
A	1								
B	0.747**	1							
C	0.704**	0.858**	1						
D	0.635**	0.672**	0.719**	1					
E	0.661**	0.740**	0.811**	0.784**	1				
F	0.572**	0.631**	0.636**	0.683**	0.722**	1			
G	0.612**	0.625**	0.661**	0.648**	0.700**	0.780**	1		
H	0.600**	0.636**	0.663**	0.678**	0.729**	0.788**	0.908**	1	
I	0.569**	0.568**	0.573**	0.677**	0.664**	0.815**	0.859**	0.887**	1

** at 0.01 level (double tail), the correlation was significant.

A: Financial responsibility, B: Legal liability, C: Ethical responsibility, D: Charitable responsibility, E: Environmental responsibility, F: Purchase intentions, G: Capacity-based trust, H: Integrity-based trust, I: Consistent -based trust.

The above section tests the correlation between variables of tourism corporate social responsibility perception, purchase intention and trust through correlation analysis. In this section, regression analysis is further adopted to explore the causal

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relationship between factors. In this part, stepwise regression analysis is used to further reveal the relationship between variables.

Original explained variables: purchase intention; Original explanatory variables: economic responsibility, legal responsibility, ethical responsibility, charitable responsibility, environmental responsibility. After the first step-by-step analysis, the significance value of the influence coefficient of legal responsibility and environmental responsibility on the "purchase intention" is 0.453 and 0.388 respectively, both >0.05, and the significance test is not passed. Therefore, economic responsibility, ethical responsibility and charitable responsibility remain, when these two independent variables are removed. The following hypotheses are rejected: H2: the legal responsibility of tourism enterprises has a positive impact on tourist purchase intention; H5: the environmental responsibility of tourism enterprises has a positive impact on tourist purchase intention.

Therefore, model explained variables: purchase intention; explanatory variables: economic responsibility, ethical responsibility, charitable responsibility.

As shown in the Table 11, the R squared of the model after adjustment is 0.513, indicating that the model has good goodness of fit and good fitting effect. The significance is infinitely close to 0<0.05, indicating that the partial regression coefficients in the model are non-0, and the regression equation of the model is reasonable. According to Table 12, the collinearity diagnosis results show that the observed values of the VIF statistics of the respective variables of the model are all <10, the model equation is feasible. After screening independent variables, the significance values of the influence coefficients of economic responsibility, ethical responsibility and charitable responsibility on "purchase intention" were 0.037, 0.001 and infinitely close to 0, all <0.05, indicating that the influence coefficients of the model were significant. Therefore, the model equation is as follows:

$$\text{Purchase intention} = 2.031 + 0.119 * \text{Economic responsibility} + 0.195 * \text{Ethical responsibility} + 0.569 * \text{Charitable responsibility}$$

In other words, economic responsibility, ethical responsibility and charitable responsibility all have a significant positive effect on the "purchase intention". The better the tourist perception of "economic responsibility, ethical responsibility and charitable responsibility" of tourism enterprises, the stronger the tourist purchase intention. The influence coefficients of the three are 0.119, 0.195 and 0.569 respectively. Thus, it is verified that "H1: Economic responsibility of tourism enterprises has a positive impact on tourist purchase intention; H3: Ethical responsibility of tourism enterprises has a positive impact on tourist purchase intention; H4: Charitable responsibility of tourism enterprises has a positive impact on tourist purchase intention" is established.

Table 11. Model Parameters

Model Parameters						
R	The square of R	the adjusted square of R	the error of estimation	of standard	F	significance
a 755	a 720	0.519	0.513		88.324	b 000

Table 12 Regression Coefficients of the Model

	Unnormalized coefficient	Standard error	Normalized coefficient	t	Significant significance	Collinear statistics	
	B		β			Tolerance	VIF
(constant)	2.031	0.811		2.506	0.013		
Economic responsibility	0.119	0.057	0.136	2.102	0.037	0.47	2.126
Ethical responsibility	0.195	0.06	0.231	3.217	0.001	0.38	2.628
Charity responsibility	0.569	0.087	0.431	6.53	0	0.45	2.224

AMOS software was used to conduct mediation effect analysis. According to the Bootstrap test results in the table below(table 13): The 95%CI percentile of direct effect, indirect effect and total effect in the model of tourism corporate social responsibility on tourist purchasing intention do not contain 0, indicating that the three effects have reached the level of

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significance. Thus, there are significant direct effect and indirect effect at the same time, which means that this model is a partial mediation model. Verify hypothesis: "H6: consumer trust plays a partial mediating role between social responsibility and purchase intention "is established.

Table 13. Mediating Effect

	Point estimate	Product of coefficients		0.95 CI percentile	
		SE	z	lower	upper
Tourism Corporate Social Responsibility Trust - Purchase Intention	0.496	0.167	2.9701	0.186	0.865
Direct effects					
Tourism Corporate Social Responsibility Trust - Purchase Intention	0.610	0.155	3.9355	0.356	0.950
Indirect effects					
Tourism Corporate Social Responsibility Trust - Purchase Intention	1.106	0.167	6.6228	0.852	1.507
Total effects					

The results showed that $P=0.7217>0.05$ (table 14), which means the significance test was not passed. Thus, the null hypothesis that "H7:trust propensity plays a moderating role in the relationship between corporate social responsibility of tourism enterprises and tourist purchase intention", is rejected.

Table 14. Moderating Effect

	R2-chng	F	df1	df2	p
Tourism Social Responsibility of * Trust propensity	.0002	.1271	1.0000	246.0000	.7217

In total, this paper constructs a model of "the impact of tourism corporate social responsibility on tourist purchasing intentions". Social responsibility is divided into five dimensions, and the mediating role of "trust" and the moderating role of "trust propensity" are discussed, thus setting up seven hypotheses. According to the data analysis results, hypothesis H2, H5 and H7 are not valid, while other hypotheses are valid.

Table 15. Summary of the Study Hypothesis Exploration Results

Study hypotheses	Rejection/Acceptance
H1: Economic responsibility of tourism enterprises has a positive impact on tourist purchasing intention	Acceptance
H2: Legal liability of tourism enterprises has a positive impact on tourist purchase intention	Refusal
H3: The ethical responsibility of tourism enterprises has a positive impact on tourist purchasing intention	Acceptance
H4: The charitable responsibility of tourism enterprises has a positive impact on tourist purchasing intention	Acceptance
H5: The environmental responsibility of tourism enterprises has a positive impact on tourist purchasing intention	Refusal
H6: Consumer trust plays a partial mediating role between social responsibility and purchase intention	Acceptance
H7: Trust propensity plays a moderating role in the relationship between tourism corporate social responsibility and tourist purchase intention	Refusal

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V. DISCUSSION

Although scholars have begun to pay attention to the study of tourism corporate social responsibility, research is insufficient, so far at least. The results of this paper confirm most of the assumptions in the study model. In the tourism corporate social responsibility model constructed, economic responsibility, ethical responsibility and charitable responsibility all have a significant positive impact on tourist purchasing intention, while the effect of legal liability and environmental liability don't. The reason may be that tourists believe that legal responsibility is the one that tourism enterprises should assume during the epidemic. And tourism enterprises bear legal responsibilities actively and correctly during the epidemic period for the legality and long-term development of their own compliance, rather than for other stakeholders, especially consumers. On the other hand, due to the background of COVID-19, people may pay more attention to the prevention and control of the epidemic, the impact of environmental responsibility of tourism enterprises on tourists is weakened. Therefore, the study results show that the impact on their purchase intention is not significant.

The study also supports the finding of a mediating role of trust between tourism corporate social responsibility and tourist purchase intention, which is consistent with conclusion of Tian et al.(2020). However, The mediating effect of trust propensity has not been proved.

Tourism companies should incorporate social responsibility into their long-term management plans. Tourism enterprises should undertake social responsibilities while ensuring the quality of tourism products, as tourists will have trust in tourism enterprises by doing this. However, tourist perception of tourism corporate social responsibility behavior is delayed. Therefore, in order to improve tourist purchase intention, tourism enterprises must take long-term actions in social responsibility, so as to bring considerable economic benefits to the enterprises.

VII. CONCLUSION

This study has theoretical and practical significance. This paper studying the impact of tourism corporate social responsibility (economic responsibility, legal responsibility, ethical responsibility, charitable responsibility and environmental responsibility) on tourists' purchasing intentions contributes to the bridging the gap of few studies of tourism corporate social responsibility. Research on the relationship between corporate social responsibility and consumers has been one of the trends in CSR research field since the last century, and many academic achievements have been accumulated till now. However, few scholars consider the characteristics of the industry when conducting research on corporate social responsibility. There is almost no researches on tourism corporate social responsibility, which has only begun to gain real attention in recent years. On the other hand, researches on the impact of CSR on purchase intention mainly focused on public welfare undertakings, environmental protection and labor protection, and lacks a comprehensive understanding of CSR (Zhou Zucheng and Zhang Yijie, 2007). Moreover, the paper innovatively added "trust" and "trust propensity" as intermediate variables, and explored the mediating effects and moderating effects respectively, which can provide some reference for academic research.

In recent years, more and more tourism enterprises undertake social responsibility actively. However, in the development process of the tourism industry, there are still endless problems exposed to the public, especially during the epidemic. The research, which explored the impact of tourism enterprises' social responsibility on tourists' purchasing intentions during COVID-19, intuitively show the data and conclusions in front of the public, so that they can realize the benefits and value of actively assuming social responsibility. In addition, it can play the role of reminding tourists, improving tourists' awareness of social responsibility. It is also an authoritative form of supervision and feedback, which standardizing the industry.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Both of the authors have contributed to this research.

DISCLOSURE STATEMENT

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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